

AUTOMATION OF THE AIR FILTRATION SYSTEM AT THE ANDEX ENTERPRISE

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Annotation. Nowadays, the process of air purification can be carried out in various ways. In 2004, the most comprehensive document setting standards for the amount of dust in the air came into force. This is "International Standard GOST ISO 14644-1-2002, Cleanrooms and Related Controlled Environments, Part 1, Classification of Air Purity". Previously, there was GOST R 50776-95, which differed in the ratio of the content of microorganisms, and the values of the amount of dust were not rounded. Given that we need instructions on the concentration of dust, these two GOST data are combined in one table. Then, under the influence of centrifugal inertia force, suspended solid particles (for example, dust particles) hit the wall of the cyclone, together with the air, they fall to the bottom of the casing and exit through the outlet port. Purified air moves through the pipe, forms an internal draft and goes out. Sikon may contain fibers and similar materials. On the other hand, thicker fabric makes it harder for air to seep through, which in turn causes some problems..

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Introduction. The air filtration system automation devices at the ANDEX enterprise carry out filtration in the condition that is caused by the composition of the air in the enterprise. Determining the amount of dust in the air and performing the air filtration process is carried out on the basis of sophisticated technologies. There are many air cleaning devices, including inertial collectors, including cyclones, barriers, shutters, and rotating propellers. Since gravitational forces on a particle are proportional to the square of the diameter and inertial forces are proportional to the cube of the diameter, the inertial (removal) force becomes relatively large as the particle diameter increases. Therefore, inertial collectors are most effective for larger particles. Inertia also depends on particle mass, with heavier particles being more efficiently removed by inertial collectors.

We all know that determining the amount of dust in the air is not a serious problem today. The process of air filtration in production areas and workshops - this system consists of two methods of filtration: 1 incoming and 2 withdrawing, the beneficial qualities of these two systems lead to improved air exchange. Similar to the previous method, there are tools for filtering and adjusting incoming air masses.

This type allows creating the necessary conditions in the building, adjusting the level of incoming harmful air masses, using the necessary fabrics or chemical compounds, ensuring the retention of harmful substances in the air by its composition is of great importance. Filtering of air masses coming from outside is also included in the functional capabilities of the unit.

Air purification is divided into simple, medium and complex technologies.

Simple technology is considered to be enough to use the simplest cyclones for air cleaning

Average air purifiers have the ability to trap dust particles in the air along with ventilation. [1], etc. Advanced technologies, these devices are also equipped with microcontrollers in terms of operation, special programs are written, and air supply is equipped in accordance with the operating conditions together with the analysis of air output and input parameters.

The dust contained in Havani belongs to the group of dry dust collectors. In fact, "Cyclone" is derived from the Greek word, which means "circular movement". The cyclone was invented in 1886 by the German inventor

M.S. It was created by Mard. A cyclone is a device that cleans dusty air from solid dust particles under the influence of centrifugal forces [2], and X-ray . Here are 3 different types of cyclones. Cyclone A sucks in air and expels

gases and dust upward through inertia. B Cyclone is made of fabrics in its internal structure and is based on the retention of dust and other small particles [3].

The amount of dust in the air can be very different. In the continuous green area, above lakes and rivers, the amount of dust in the air is less than 1 mg / m³, in industrial cities - 3-10 mg / m³, in cities with inconvenient streets - up to 20 mg/m³. Particle sizes from 0.02 to 100 μm.

Today's sanitary standards - (SN 245-71) limit the average daily maximum permissible concentration of non-toxic dust in the atmospheric air of settlements to 0.15 mg/m³, but in fact, the concentration of dust is often higher ladi, so it is better to use experimental data on the level of air pollution in a certain area. [4]. Air purifiers remove some of the harmful substances and particles from the air, thus improving the working conditions.

Due to their extremely small size, harmful substances pass through a standard vacuum cleaner bag and are re-distributed into the air where they remain for days. Other airborne particles, such as bacteria and viruses, can cause illnesses, some of which are fatal. There are two common types of air purifiers that remove some or all of the airborne disease and allergy-causing particles: mechanical filters—the most effective are classified as high-efficiency particulate air filters (HEPA filters)—and electrostatic precipitators .

HEPA filters are made of very fine glass filaments less than 1 micron in diametric (Figure 3.5) (micron 0.00004 inch, 0.001 mm). By comparison, a human hair is about 75 microns

(0.003 inches, 0.07 mm) in diameter. Fine glass threads are twisted together and compressed to form a filter mat. Because the individual threads are so microscopic, most of the fabric can trap harmful air. The pores in the filter are very small, typically less than 0.5 microns (0.00002 in, 0.0005 mm). HEPA filters collect particles down to 0.3 microns (0.00001 inch, 0.0003 mm) in diameter. Although the filter may only be 0.10 inches (2.5 mm) wide, it is made up of 2,500 layers of glass filaments.

Electrostatic precipitators rely on electrostatic forces to remove particles from the air. They work by creating a cloud of free electrons that dust particles are forced to pass through. As the dust particles pass through the plasma, they become charged, making them easier to collect. Electrostatic precipitators can collect particles down to 0.01 micron (0.00001 mm) in diameter [5].

A dust meter is a device designed to measure the mass concentration of dust in the exhaust gases of fuel injection devices, in working and residential areas, in atmospheric air. A certain type of device should be used for each task. As a result, in the production process, fabric processing and dyeing are being carried out rapidly.

With these things in mind, we recommend the following structure diagram of the air purification process for effective use of all technologies. [6], To date, there are several

methods of dust measurement: optical (photometric), gravimetric, piezobalance, triboelectric, radioisotope. Let's take a look at each of them:

Optical dust measurement method (photometric and nephelometric method).

The optical principle of operation is to measure the intensity of light radiation when passing through a dusty medium. The concentration of dust particles is proportional to the absorbance value, which is automatically determined and is the negative logarithm of the transmittance.

Disadvantages of the photometric absorption method:

- low sensitivity when measuring low concentrations of aerosol particles (less than 30 mg/m³), as well as inability to control high concentrations (more than 10...12 g/m³). almost complete absorption of light radiation [7].

When automating various technological processes, it is necessary to obtain information about their indicators. Primary transducers (or sensors) are widely used for this purpose.

As a sensor, the physico-chemical properties of aerosols have a high influence on the measurement result (aerosol size, composition and color). In order to reduce the measurement error, it is necessary to calibrate the device for a specific type of aerosol or to introduce a correction factor

Mechanical converters are characterized by changing mechanical input parameters (pressure, power, speed, consumption, etc.) to mechanical output parameters (rotational frequency, pressure, etc.). Elastic elements (membrane, spring, hammer, etc.), flaps, vanes and throttle devices are used as sensitive elements of such switches.

The FSR sensor used in this study was an Interlink-402 that could measure the force values up to 100 g–10 kg. The FSR is composed of a flexible substrate with a printed semi-conductor, flexible substrate with interdigitating electrode, and spacer adhesive. FSR is quite cheap and

easily used with a small size (the diameter of the sensing area is 12.7 mm) and thin thickness (thickness of 0.45). FSR is not as accurate as the load cell or the strain gauge, however, it can reduce measurement errors or use relative comparisons through individual calibration.

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